

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute
www.ejppri.eg.net

Extraction, physicochemical characterization, and toxicity evaluation of neem oil nanoemulsion formulations for control of fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)

Naira, S. Elmasry and Eman, A. Shehata

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 11/11/2025

Accepted: 28/12/2025

Keywords

Neem seed oil, neem nano-formulations, insecticidal activity, chemical analyses and fall armyworm.

Abstract

It is commonly recognized that the neem tree contains active ingredients such as nimbin, nimbidin, and azadirachtin. Neem oil contains high concentrations of these active ingredients. Neem oil's advantageous ability to eradicate pests with no negative effects on the environment makes it a very appealing alternative to synthetic chemical pesticides. Neem seeds were extracted using Soxhlet extraction and cold maceration, respectively, to produce the oil extract. Neem seed oil extract yielded 28.11% after extraction. Using the high-energy emulsification method, neem oil was formulated as nanoemulsions with water and nonionic surfactants, polysorbate 80 (PS₈₀), and alkylpolyglucoside (APG). Viscosity measurements and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy analysis were used to characterize the produced neem seed oil extract. Utilizing Transmission Electron Microscopy, the produced nano-formulations were characterized. The toxicity of the neem oil extract used to control the invasion of fall armyworms, *Spodoptera frugiperda* (J. E. Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Neem seed oil extract's estimated LC₅₀ values were 2.16%, 1.44%, 1.18%, and 0.92% after 6, 12, 24, and 48 hours, respectively. Using the food impregnation procedure. After just 12 hours of exposure using the food impregnation method, the formulation consisting of neem oil extract and 2 milliliters per kilogram of PS₈₀ surfactant resulted in 100% death. The plant protection research laboratory conducted toxicological studies from October 2024 to May 2025. According to the findings, neem oil extract nanoemulsions with nonionic surfactants have a lot of potential as a natural pesticide for controlling fall armyworm larvae in their 3rd instar. The present study also aimed to study the toxic effects of neem extract only and with the two nanoemulsion formulations, and to investigate the adverse effects of the prepared formulations on different enzyme chemical analyses of the tested insect. The chemical enzymes were aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), glutathione s-transferase (GST), serum creatinine, and total protein activity using serum of 3rd instar larvae of fall armyworm after treatment with half lethal concentration.

Introduction

Fall armyworm, also known as *Spodoptera frugiperda* (J.E. Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), is a moth whose larvae consumes over 100 plant species (FAO and CABI, 2019). Numerous crops, including maize, peanuts, rice, wheat, sugarcane, and many others, are known to be seriously harmed by it (Benson, 2017). Fresh leaves in maize are destroyed by fall armyworm larvae, which hinders crop growth and eventually lowers production. According to current reports, fall armyworm is found in more than 40 tropical and southern African nations (Benson, 2017). Many farmers utilize synthetic chemical pesticides to reduce the loss caused by fall armyworm infestation. However, there are unanticipated negative effects of using synthetic chemical insecticides, including residues in food and water (Schmutterer, 1990, and Paragas *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, it is well recognized that beneficial insects are killed by synthetic pesticides, such as herbicides and insecticides (Abraham *et al.*, 2018, and Blibech *et al.*, 2015). In addition, pesticides such as carbamates and organophosphates can have detrimental impacts on health (Paragas *et al.*, 2018, and Daniel and Baker, 2013). The environmentally friendly insecticides of several plants have been assessed, including azadirachtin, nicotine, pyrethrin, rotenone, ryania, sabadilla, and spinosad (Rajashekar *et al.*, 2013). They are noted for being biodegradable and having a low toxicity to species that are not their intended target. Because of this, these pesticides can be used in integrated pest management programs (Nawaz and Mabubu, 2016). For example, the neem tree yields asteroid-like azadirachtin, which contains a variety of bioactive components (Paul *et al.*, 2011). It has antiviral, antifungal, antipyorrheic, insecticidal, larvicidal, nematocidal,

antiallergenic, and antifeedant qualities (Pankaj *et al.*, 2011). Neem oil or almond oil nanoemulsions for vitamin E administration were investigated by Rinaldi *et al.* 2022 "Assessment of Antioxidant and Anti-Inflammatory Activity"(Rinaldi *et al.*, 2022).

Neem is a perennial green tree that is grown in nearly 30 nations (Rajendran *et al.*, 2012). Phenolic compounds found in neem tree extract (*Azadirachta indica*) have antioxidant properties related to free radical scavenging, singlet oxygen quenching, metal ion chelation, hydrogen donation, and their function as substrates for free radicals like superoxide anion and hydroxyl radical, which may influence their toxic action toward non-targeted organisms (Gupta and Sharma, 2006). Particle size and shape, crystal structure, chemical composition, and surface area are examples of physicochemical features that are significant in comprehending the hazardous effects of the studied materials. Additionally, it has been demonstrated that higher surface reactivity is predictive of higher biological activity (Oberdörster *et al.*, 2007). Its mode of action, which includes growth retardation, molting inhibition, inducing deformity in the larval stage, or interfering with larval growth and development, is the basis for its insecticidal effect (Dimetry, 2012). Additionally, neem oil is a universally used broad-spectrum botanical insecticide for protecting stored grains (Costa *et al.*, 2014, and Choupanian *et al.*, 2017). Neem oil's insecticidal effectiveness is known to be influenced by how it is applied (Gahukar, 2014).

If the seeds of neem are linked to nanosystems like liposomes, nanostructured carriers, and nanoemulsions (NEs), which are prospective substitutes for traditional formulations, the active compound's lipophilicity can be enhanced (Alhasso

et al., 2022, and Ren *et al.*, 2022). NEs are specifically colloidal systems that are stabilized by combinations of surfactants. Neem oil NEs have been shown to have antioxidant activity, which supports their biological impact even when the oil is formulated as a nanoemulsion (Rinaldi *et al.*, 2017). It has been shown that neem oil can scavenge free radicals and lessen the harm that ROS do to cells. Normalizing lipid peroxidation and reducing ROS-mediated cell death are two benefits of using neem oil (Sarkar *et al.*, 2021). Because of its numerous biological benefits and lack of hemolytic activity, this oil is especially well-suited for use in medicinal formulations (Blum *et al.*, 2019). The main active ingredient primarily present in neem seeds is azadirachtin. The chemical structure of azadirachtin is $C_{35}H_{44}O_{16}$. Azadirachtin functions as an insect toxin because it can interfere with the synthesis of the hormone ecdysone, which causes the insects to wither and eventually die. Additionally, azadirachtin might obstruct and smother insects' breathing apertures (Cloyd, 2015). Depending on the kind of bug, azadirachtin's minimum lethal dose varies. Ex. *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae have an LD₅₀ of 1.00 ppm (Blaney and Simmonds, 1990). Emulsion can be an appealing form to create neem oil as a biopesticide because the insect's lethal dose is significantly lower than the quantity of azadirachtin in the neem oil. Nanoemulsions with droplet sizes between 20 and 200 nm are referred to as O/W (Oil in water) or W/O (Water in oil). Compared to microscale emulsions, nanoemulsions feature a number of intriguing physical characteristics. Neem seed oil was prepared in a nanoemulsion by Ghotbi in 2014.

In order to suppress Choupanian and Omar (2018) studied the physicochemical characterization and

formulation of neem oil nanoemulsions. Non-ionic emulsifiers can be more successful in terms of stability and emulsification than ionic ones (Tadros, 2012). Simple pipe flow, rotor-stator systems, and high-pressure valve homogenizers are the devices that supply this energy for the emulsion system to form (Tadros, 2012). A 31.03 nm nanoemulsion was created using high-energy sonication, and it was demonstrated that the emulsions were effective against *Cx. Quinquifasciatus* (Anjali *et al.*, 2012). Additionally, ultrasonic waves were used to create a 50.21 nm-sized nanoemulsion (Ghotbi, 2014). Using a homogenizer, the emulsification procedure was carried out at room temperature. Ramadhany *et al.* 2021 investigated the oil-in-water (O/W) emulsion based on neem as a biopesticide. Neem extracts were used as a natural pesticide against fall armyworms by Tulashie *et al.* in 2021. Also, the toxicity of neem, citronella, castor, and clove oil against *S. frugiperda* was investigated by Dono *et al.* 2020.

This study intended to determine the half-lethal concentration (LC₅₀) and lethal concentration (LC₉₀) of two different neem oil and nanoemulsion formulations against *S. frugiperda* by extracting, characterizing, and evaluating the toxicity of two neem oil nanoemulsions against 3rd instar larvae using the food impregnation method. Using serum from third-instar fall armyworm larvae treated with half-lethal concentrations, examine the harmful effects of the two nanoemulsion formulations and the toxic effects of neem extract alone on various chemical analyses, such as aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), glutathione s-transferase (GST), serum creatinine, and total protein activity.

Materials and methods

1. Preparation of neem seed kernel cake:

Fully ripe neem trees from the Delta zone (Plant Protection Institute Farm) were used to produce fresh neem seeds. To maximize extraction efficiency and facilitate the removal of the seed kernel with the seed coat, the seeds were then sun-dried for one week. Then, to make neem seed kernel cake, the neem seed kernel was mashed in a hand blender. A large surface area was created for extraction by grinding. To eliminate all moisture content, the seed kernel cake was roasted at 60°C for 15 minutes before extraction (Tulashie *et al.*, 2021).

2. Extraction processes and preparation of nano neem oil formulations:

2.1. Using Soxhlet extraction to extract neem oil:

After being heated to 80°C, 100 g of pulverized neem seed kernel cake was placed in a thimble. After that, cotton wool was used to plug the thimble, which was then put inside the Soxhlet chamber. To guarantee a good extraction of the neem oil, 800 ml of a 3:2 hexane and ethanol mixture was put into a 1-liter round-bottom flask. The condenser unit and the circulator with cold water were then connected to the Soxhlet apparatus to cool the increasing solvent vapor (Dono *et al.*, 2020). A heating mantle running at 45°C served as the heat source. To finish the extraction process, the procedure was carried out multiple times for roughly 20 refluxes over ten to sixteen hours. Following cooling, the extracted mixture was concentrated using a rotary evaporator set up at 40°C and 6.5 bar of decreased pressure, which allowed for the recovery of the majority of the solvent in each extract mixture. After concentration, the neem oil was put in an evaporating dish and kept in a desiccator until it was needed.

2.2. Making nanoemulsions (Alaa *et al.*, 2022):

Two nanoemulsions were made using a variation of the technique outlined by Jerobin *et al.* (2012); emulsions were prepared using (Neem oil / PS₈₀) and (Neem oil / APG). Neem oil and distilled water were diluted in a 1:1 (O/W) ratio to create nano-emulsion formulations. As an emulsifier, 2% PS₈₀ and APG were used. They were supplied by Cognis Oleochemicals. An ultrasonic cleaner set (Model WUCDO 3H, 300W and 40 Hz, Germany) was used to sonicate the resulting emulsion for 60 minutes. A high-energy ultrasonication probe was then used for 5 minutes, and the ultrasonic cleaner was used again for 30 min. while cooling with an ice bath. The resultant emulsion was then mixed for an additional 60 minutes and sonicated as previously described, and a suitable volume of CaCl₂ (1:5 CaCl₂ to alginate, respectively) was added.

3. Characterization of neem seed oil extract by Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy analysis:

A Nicolet 550 FTIR spectrometer with 128 scans and a resolution of 4cm⁻¹ was used to perform FT-IR analysis in the mid-IR (400–4000cm⁻¹) area to identify several distinctive functional groups found in the neem seed oil extract. After combining the sample with KBr (1–100 mg), it is pressed onto a thin wafer that is placed within an infrared cell, and the spectrum is then recorded. The values of the recorded infrared (IR) spectra are represented as λ_{\max} cm⁻¹.

4. Characterization of the prepared nanoformulations using Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM):

A high-resolution (200 kV) electron microscope (JEOL-JEM-2100) was used to measure the particle size and TEM picture. A suspension of tiny sample powders was dipped onto a

copper grip covered in holey carbon foil to create TEM samples, which were then allowed to dry at room temperature.

5. Stability and viscosity test of nanoformulation emulsions:

Creaming tests are used to measure the stability of emulsions (Ramadhany *et al.*, 2021). Samples are kept at room temperature for two weeks; if no creaming occurs, the emulsion is deemed stable. In cases of creaming, the heights of several phases are compared. At room temperature, the Ostwald Viscometer is used to test the emulsion's viscosity. Analysis of emulsifiers and neem oil, the emulsifying power of the emulsifier was examined. The effectiveness of each emulsifier in reducing the surface tension of water was assessed by measuring its emulsifying power (Choupanian and Omar (2018)). We measured the surface tension using a De-Nöuy tensiometer K-6 with a platinum ring.

6. Preparation of varying concentrations of neem oil extract and its nanoemulsions:

Pipetting varying quantities of neem oil (1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, and 5 cm³) into distinct 100 ml volumetric flasks allowed for the preparation of various concentrations of neem oil extract. Each volumetric flask was filled to the 100 ml mark with 95% ethanol as the dilution solvent, yielding concentrations of 1.0%, 2.0%, 3.0%, 4.0%, and 5.0% v/v, respectively. Additionally, neem oil nanoemulsions were made using the same five strengths of neem oil and 2% alkylpolyglucoside (APG) or polysorbate (PS₈₀).

7. Collection and rearing of fall armyworms *Spodoptera frugiperda*:

Fall armyworm larvae were gathered from two distinct insecticide-free cornfields near Mansoura University. The experiments were conducted on subsequent generations. Until they

pupated, the larvae were fed bits of maize leaves that had not been treated with insecticide. For aeration, pupae were individually moved into 500 ml deli cups with fine mesh coverings. For mass raising and mating, emerged adults were moved into Bug Dorm cages of 30 × 40 × 30 cm. Maize seedlings were given to the adult moths as an oviposition substrate. To prevent cannibalism, the larvae in their second instar that emerged from the eggs were placed individually into deli cups. Bioassays were conducted using larvae in their third instar.

8. Measurement of chemical analysis:

Serum samples were taken during the experiment after third-instar larvae were treated with a half-lethal concentration. The tissue samples were weighed and homogenized at a 1:2 w/v ratio in 1 milliliter of diluted water (pH 7.0) (Alaa *et al.*, 2022). Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) were measured using the Reitman and Frankel (1957) technique. Glutathione S-transferase (GST) was measured using spectrophotometry using the Habig *et al.* (1974) technique. The method of Tobias *et al.* (1962) was used to evaluate the serum creatinine. The method outlined by Bradford (1976) was used to determine the total protein content. Data were subjected to statistical analysis by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results and discussion

1. Analysis by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR):

The different functional groups of the components in the neem seed oil extract were identified using the FTIR analysis technique (Figure 1). Table (1) lists several functional categories found in the extract.

Figure (1): The Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy analysis technique of the neem seed oil extract.

Table (1): Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy results indicating the functional groups present in the neem seed oil extract.

Peaks Name	Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Functional group (Bond)
1	590.15	Alkyl-halide (C-I (stretch))
2	722.13	Alkane (C-H (bend))
3	1120.10	Ether (C-O (stretch))
4	1160.16	Alcohol (C-O (stretch))
5	1240.31	Acyl (C-O(stretch))
6	1458.60	Alkane (C-H(bend))
7	1740.73	Carbonyl (C=O(stretch))
8	2860.03	Alkane (C-H (stretch))
9	2931.18	Alkane (C-H (stretch))
10	3400.27	1,2 Amine [aliphatic] (N-H(stretch))

2. Characterization of Neem oil nanoemulsions:

2.1. Electron microscopy examination:

A Transmission electron microscope (TEM) was used to investigate the synthesized neem oil nano-emulsions. TEM data revealed that the sizes of the nanoparticles ranged from 20 to 60 nm,

and nearly all of the neem oil nanoemulsions that were made with 2% PS₈₀ had spherical, smooth surfaces (Figure 2.A). When 2% APG was added to the generated neem oil nanoemulsion, the particle sizes grew to 40–70.2 nm, larger than the emulsion particles (Figure 2.B).

Figure (2): Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images, A) Neem oil nanoemulsion with adding 2% of PS₈₀. and B) Neem oil nanoemulsion with adding 2% of alkylpolyglucoside.

2.2. UV spectrophotometric examinations:

1 gm of the loaded nanoemulsions was refluxed with 15 mL of methanol at 70°C to assess the active component contents (Azadirachtin in neem oil) of the nanoemulsions. For one hour, refluxing was maintained in order to guarantee full oil extraction. After that, the samples were centrifuged for fifteen minutes. At a wavelength of 214 nm, the absorbance of methanol containing the extracted quantity of azadirachtin was measured (Jerobin *et al.*, 2012).

2.3. Stability, viscosity, and surface tension tests of emulsions:

Creaming tests are used to measure the stability of emulsions. Samples are kept at room temperature for two weeks; if no creaming occurs, the emulsion is deemed stable (Ramadhany *et al.*, 2021). In cases of creaming, the heights of several phases are compared. At room temperature, the Ostwald Viscometer is used to test the emulsion's viscosity. At 40 degrees Celsius, it was found that neem oil had a high viscosity of about 42 cP (Water has a viscosity of 1 cP). Neem oil's spreadability is hindered by its high viscosity. When 2% PS₈₀ is added, the viscosity of the neem oil nanoemulsion is approximately 34 cP, and when 2% APG is added, the viscosity is around 36 cP. In this study, each emulsifier was mixed with water at varying quantities to determine its emulsifying power. The capillary pipe method was used to analyze the water mixture's surface tension at room temperature. At room temperature, the surface tension of pure water is originally 0.0722 N/m. The surface tension of the neem oil nanoemulsion with 2% PS₈₀ was more effective than 2% APG at reducing the surface tension of the water mixture. Neem oil nanoemulsion with 2% PS₈₀ was able to reduce the surface tension of the water mixture to 0.030 N/m at a concentration of 10 ppm, whereas 2%

APG only managed to achieve 0.035 N/m, compared with the neem oil water mixture with a surface tension of 0.045 N/m.

3. Laboratory toxicity bioassay:

Fall armyworm larvae were used to investigate the toxicity of five different concentrations of neem extract (i.e., 1.0%, 2.0%, 3.0%, 4.0%, and 5.0% v/v) and the control. Third instar fall armyworm larvae were used as subjects for each concentration. Because this stage of the life cycle is when fall armyworm most frequently damages maize and other plants in the tropics and other regions of the world, third-instar larvae were utilized for bioassays (Sukontason *et al.*, 2004, and FAO and CABI, 2019). After cutting fresh maize leaves into 2-by-4-cm pieces, they were dipped in the extract for a minute, and the runoff was left to drain. As the extract concentration rises, so does the larval mortality rate. Neem seed oil has shown greater potency, achieving over 60% mortality at a concentration of 2.0 v/v rather than over 75% mortality after 24 hours at a slightly higher concentration of 3.0 v/v. Furthermore, following exposure times of 24 and 48 hours, 100% mortality was attained by neem seed oil extract at 4 and 5 v/v. Neem seed oil extract had a quicker effect (Mortality) on *S. frugiperda* larvae at greater concentrations. After 6, 12, 24, and 48 hrs., the LC₅₀ values for total mortality were 2.92%, 2.37%, 1.28%, and 1.12%, respectively. Additionally, as seen in Table (2), the LC₉₀ for total mortality after 6, 12, 24, and 48 hours was 5.26%, 4.15%, 2.31%, and 2.01%, respectively. After 24 hours, a 2% APG addition to a neem oil nanoemulsion produced over 70% mortality at a 2.0 v/v concentration, whereas a slightly higher concentration of 3.0 v/v produced over 90% mortality. Furthermore, after exposure times of 12 and 24 hours, 100% mortality was attained at 4 and 5 v/v using a neem oil

nanoemulsion that had 2% APG added. After 6, 12, 24, and 48 hrs., the LC₅₀ for total mortality was 2.16, 1.44, 1.18, and 0.92%, respectively. However, after 24 hours, a slightly higher concentration of 3.0 v/v produced 100% mortality, while a 2% PS₈₀ addition to the neem oil nanoemulsion produced over 80% mortality at 2.0 v/v. Furthermore, during exposure times of 12 and 24 hours, it attained 100% mortality at 3, 4, and 5 v/v. After 6, 12, 24, and 48 hrs., the LC₅₀ values for total mortality were

1.49, 1.09, 0.83, and 0.62%, respectively.

In general, *S. frugiperda* mortality varied according to the type of nanoemulsion formulation added to neem oil extract and the rising concentration of neem oil extract. Within 12 hrs. of treatment, 100% of the larvae died when 3.0, 4.0, and 5.0% v/v concentrations of the neem seed oil extract nanoemulsion were consumed along with 2% of APG or PS₈₀ (Table 3).

Table (2): Percentage mortality of 3rd instar larvae of the fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*) treated with five concentrations of neem seed oil extract.

Concentration (v/v) %	% larval mortality			
	after 6 hrs.	after 12 hrs.	after 24 hrs.	after 48 hrs.
Control	0	2	5.0	7.5
1.0	17.1	21.7	38.9	44.61
2.0	37.7	49.9	66.5	70.20
3.0	65.4	72.2	79.7	80.23
4.0	79.5	89.6	95.0	100
5.0	88.7	99.2	100.0	100
LC ₅₀	2.92	2.37	1.28	1.12
LC ₉₀	5.26	4.15	2.31	2.01

Table (3): Percentage mortality of 3rd instar larvae of fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*) treated with two nanoemulsion formulations of neem alkylpolyglucoside and neem Polys after 6, 12, 24 and 48 hrs.

Concentration (v/v) %	% larval mortality of neem/alkylpolyglucoside				% larval mortality of neem/PS ₈₀			
	after 6 hrs.	after 12 hrs.	after 24 hrs.	after 48 hrs.	after 6 hrs.	after 12 hrs.	after 24 hrs.	after 48 hrs.
Control	1	2.5	6.0	8.0	2	3	7.5	8.0
1.0	23.1	34.7	42.10	54.08	33.5	45.79	60.10	80.15
2.0	45.3	54.80	72.3	82.60	52.2	60.91	81.7	94.44
3.0	71.5	84.6	94.7	100	79.9	95.8	100	100
4.0	85.7	99.6	100	100	97.8	100	100	100
5.0	99.03	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
LC ₅₀	2.16	1.44	1.18	0.92	1.49	1.09	0.83	0.62
LC ₉₀	3.89	2.59	2.14	1.66	2.69	1.96	1.50	1.12

4. Chemical enzyme serum analysis measurements:

4.1. Serum aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT):

According to the data in Table (4), neem seed oil extract significantly reduced AST activity, reaching -

15.71% and -37.15% when treated with LC₅₀ using the extract alone and the extract plus nanoemulsion. 2% polysorbate 80, followed by a considerable rise to +16.38% when 2% APG was added in comparison to the control value. The (AST) activity was significantly increased using

nanoemulsion formulations. When using neem seed oil extract alone and extract with nanoemulsion 2% of APG, the nano-emulsions significantly reduced (ALT) activity, reaching -11.37% and -8.58% with LC₅₀, respectively. Furthermore, the addition of 2% PS₈₀ nano neem emulsion resulted in a notable rise to +14.03 percent.

4.2. Hepatic glutathione S-transferase (GST):

Table (4): Aspartate aminotransferase, Alanine aminotransferase, and glutathione S-transferase activity in the serum of 3rd instar larvae of the fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*) after treatment with the LC₅₀ of different nano neem emulsion formulations.

Tested compound	Aspartate aminotransferase (units/mL)		Alanine aminotransferase (units/mL)		Glutathione s- transferase (nmol/min/mg protein)	
	Mean enzyme activity	Change %	Mean enzyme activity	Change %	Mean enzyme activity	Change %
Control	11.17±1.75 ^a	---	25.16±0.72 ^a	---	22.25±0.01 ^b	
Neem seed oil extract	9.42±0.68 ^{b,c}	-15.71	22.30±0.24 ^a	-11.37	18.65±0.02 ^c	-16.18
Neem/alkylpolyglucoside	13.00±1.10 ^{a,b}	+16.38	23.00±0.22 ^a	-8.58	26.50±0.1 ^a	+19.10
Neem / PS ₈₀	7.02±0.40 ^c	-37.15	28.69±0.99 ^a	+14.03	15.48±0.11 ^d	-30.43
F value	12.19**		1.16 ^{NS}		138.65**	

4.3. Serum creatinine:

Table (5) contains information about serum creatinine levels, showing that there has been a substantial decline in the levels of these indicators. Significant decreases of -15.22%, -12.32%, and -47.10% were estimated for neem seed oil extract alone and extract with 2% PS₈₀ or 2% APG nanoformulations, respectively.

4.4. Determination of total proteins:

The most crucial elements of an insect's biochemistry that bind foreign

Table (5): The specific activities of glutathione S-transferase (GST) in serum of 3rd instar larvae of fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*) after treating with the LC₅₀ of the tested neem nanoformulations.

Tested compound	Creatinine (mg/dL)		Total protein (g/dL)	
	Mean enzyme activity	Change %	Mean enzyme activity	Change %
Control	1.38±0.10 ^a		12.74±0.04 ^b	
Neem seed oil extract	1.17±0.03 ^a	-15.22	11.51±0.03 ^c	-9.65
Neem /alkylpolyglucoside	1.21±0.02 ^a	-12.32	11.03±0.33 ^c	-13.42
Neem /PS ₈₀	0.73±0.03 ^b	-47.10	10.02±0.92 ^a	-21.35
F value	10.53**		153.80**	

The specific activity of glutathione S-transferase (Nmol/min/mg protein) is displayed in Table 4. Such formulations' subacute oral treatment resulted in a notable change in the enzymes' activity, which ranged from an increase to a decrease. In the instance of neem seed oil extract formulation, adding 2% of PS₈₀ nano neem emulsion resulted in a drop of -16.18%, an elevation of 19.10%, and a decline of -30.43%, respectively.

substances are proteins. According to the data in Table (5), when compared to the control, all tested new chemical formulations showed a significant decrease in total proteins (-9.65, -13.42, and -21.35 for tested synthetic chemicals, respectively). This outcome was consistent with the use of teflubenzuron and hexaflumuron on the 4th instars of *S. littoralis* by Assar *et al.* (2010).

This study looked into the possibility of using neem seed extracts as a natural insecticide to combat fall armyworm. In order to find functional groups and compounds that exhibit biological activities, such as pesticidal activity, antifeedant, and cytotoxic characteristics (Tulashie *et al.*, 2021), extracts were made using Soxhlet and cold maceration procedures. To verify the extracts' effectiveness and determine whether the chemicals and functional groups identified by the study were actually present in the extracts, laboratory toxicity bioassays were also conducted. The management of *S. frugiperda* showed 100% larval mortality after 12 hrs. and 100% larval mortality after applying 3% v/v of the extracts. Neem pesticides can be a dependable product for use in agriculture as a good substitute for synthetic insecticides since they are environmentally acceptable and extremely effective in causing FAW larval mortality. There are several bioactive components in neem oil extracts (Rinaldi *et al.*, 2022). Reactive oxygen species, or free radical toxicity, occurs when biological systems are out of balance, either because defenses are compromised or because the creation of free radicals is outpacing defenses. Additionally, emulsion stability is significantly influenced by the kind and concentration of emulsifiers used (Ramadhany *et al.*, 2021). With the lowest droplet size and no creaming, the non-ionic emulsifier provided the best emulsion stability. Smaller droplets, however, caused the viscosity to rise. As a result, it reduced the rates of larvicidal death by producing prolonged spreading and dispersion times. Larval mortality rates rose with the fastest spreading and dispersion time. The produced nanoparticles' sizes ranged from 20 to 70 nm, according to the characterization of the neem oil nano-formulation emulsions (Alaa *et al.*,

2022). The neem oil extract formulations in nanoemulsion showed greater mortality than the neem oil extract, according to the calculated LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ values. Using a high-energy emulsification technique, the neem oil and nonionic surfactants were successfully created as a nanoemulsion formulation (Choupanian and Omar, 2018). Using the food impregnation method, neem oil nanoemulsion with 2% polysorbate (PS₈₀) also showed the highest mortality rate against 3rd instar fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*) larvae in 12 hours at 3.0 mL/kg. Neem seed oil extract significantly reduced AST activity, reaching -15.71% and -37.15% when treated with LC₅₀ using the extract alone and the extract plus nanoemulsion. 2% polysorbate 80, followed by a considerable rise to +16.38% when 2% APG was added in comparison to the control value. The (AST) activity was significantly increased using nanoemulsion formulations. When using neem seed oil extract alone and extract with nanoemulsion 2% of APG, the nano-emulsions significantly reduced (ALT) activity, reaching -11.37% and -8.58% with LC₅₀, respectively. Furthermore, the addition of 2% polysorbate 80 neem emulsion resulted in a notable rise to +14.03 percent. Also, chemical analysis measurements showed that the specific activity of glutathione S-transferase (nmol/min/mg protein) was displayed changing in the enzymes' activity, which ranged from an increase to a decrease. Serum creatinine levels showed a substantial decline in the levels of these indicators, with significant decreases of -15.22%, -12.32%, and -47.10%. Also, all tested nanoemulsion formulations showed a significant decrease in total proteins (-9.65, -13.42, and -21.35 for tested synthetic chemicals, respectively).

References

- Abraham, J.; Benhotons, G.S.; Krampah, I.; Tagba, J.; Amisshah, C. and Abraham, J.D. (2018):** Commercially formulated glyphosate can kill non-target pollinator bees under laboratory conditions. *J. Entomol. Exp. Appl.*, 166: 695–702, doi.org/10.1111/eea.12694
- Alaa, E.B.; Abdel Rahman, H.A.; Nadia, Z.D. and Dalia, A.Y. (2022):** Toxicity evaluation of two neem oil nano-formulations using Swiss male albino mice. *Biomed J Sci. & Tech. Res.*, 43(4)- BJSTR. MS.ID.006928. doi: 10.26717/BJSTR.2022.43.006928
- Alhasso, B.; Ghorri, M.U. and Conway, B.R. (2022):** Systematic review on the effectiveness of essential and carrier oils as skin penetration enhancers in pharmaceutical formulations. *J. Sci Pharm.* 90(1):14. doi:10.3390/scipharm90010014
- Anjali, C.H.; Sharma, Y.; Mukherjee, A. and Chandrasekaran, N. (2012):** Neem oil (*Azadirachta indica*) nanoemulsion a potent larvicidal agent against *Culex quinquefasciatus*. *J. Pest Manag. Sci.*, 68(2):158-163. doi:10.1002/ps.2233
- Assar, A.A.; Abo El-Mahasen, M.M.; Khalil, M.E. and Mahmoud, S.H. (2010):** Biochemical effects of some insect growth regulators on the house fly, *Musca domestica* (Diptera: Muscidae). *Egy. Acad. J. of Bio. Sci.*, 2(2): 33-44. doi:10.21608/EAJBSC.2010.16261
- Benson M.F. (2017):** Fall armyworm. Bureau of Entomology and Plant Quarantine, U.S. Dept. of Agriculture. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.123807>
- Blaney, W.M. and Simmonds, M.S.J. (1990):** A behavioural and electrophysiological study of the role of tarsal chemoreceptors in feeding by adults of *Spodoptera Heliothis virescens* and *Helicoverpa armigera*. *J. of Ins. Phys.*, 36(10): 743–756. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1910\(90\)90048-K](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1910(90)90048-K)
- Blibech, I.; Ksantini, M.; Jardak, T. and Bouaziz, M. (2015):** Effect of Insecticides on *Trichogramma* Parasitoids Used in Biological Control against *Prays oleae* insect pest. *J. Advan. in Chem. Engine. and Sci.*, 5: 362-372. doi: 10.4236/aces.2015.53038
- Blum, F.C.; Singh, J. and Merrell, D.S. (2019):** In vitro activity of neem (*Azadirachta indica*) oil extract against *Helicobacter pylori*. *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 232:236–243. doi:10.1016/j.jep.2018.12.025
- Bradford, M.M. (1976):** A rapid and sensitive method for the quantitative of microgram quantities of protein utilizing the principle of protein-dye binding. *J. Analy. Biochem.*, 72(1-2): 248-254. doi:10.1016/0003-2697(76)90527-3
- Choupanian, M. and Omar, D. (2018):** Formulation and physicochemical characterization of neem oil nanoemulsions for control of *Sitophilus oryzae* (L., 1763) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) and *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst, 1797) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae). *Turkish Journal of Entomology*, 42(2): 127-139. <https://doi.org/10.16970/entoted.398541>
- Choupanian, M.; Omar, D.; Basri, M. and Asib, N. (2017):** Preparation and characterization of neem oil nanoemulsion formulations against *Sitophilus oryzae* and *Tribolium castaneum* adults. *J. of Pest. Sci.*,

- 42(4): 158-165.
doi: 10.1584/jpestics. D17-032
- Cloyd, R.A. (2015):** Western flower thrips (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) and insecticide resistance: an overview and strategies to mitigate insecticide resistance development. *J. of Entom. Sci.*, 51: 257-273. doi.org/10.18474/JES16-15.1
- Costa J.T.; Forim, M.R.; Costa, E.S.; Souza, J.R.D.; Mondego, J.M. and Junior, A.L.B. (2014):** Effects of different formulations of neem oil-based products on control *Zabrotes subfasciatus* (Boheman, 1833) (Coleoptera: Bruchidae) on beans. *J. of Stor. Prod. Res.*, 56: 49-53. doi.org/ 10.1016 /j.jspr.2013.10.004
- Daniel, C. and Baker, B. (2013):** Dispersal of *Rhagoletis cerasi* in commercial cherry orchards: Efficacy of soil covering nets for cherry fruit fly control. *J. Insects.*, 4: 168–176. doi.org/10.3390/insects4010168
- Dimetry, N.Z. (2012):** Prospects of botanical pesticides for the future in integrated pest management program (IPM) with special reference to neem uses in Egypt. *Archives of Phytopathology and Plant Protection*, 45: 1138-1161. doi:10.1080/03235408.2012.65793
- Dono, D.; Hidayat, Y.; Suganda, T.; Hidayat, S. and Widayani, N.S. (2020):** The toxicity of neem (*Azadirachta indica*), citronella (*Cymbopogon nardus*), castor (*Ricinus communis*), and clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*) oil against *Spodoptera frugiperda*. *Cropsaver Journal of Plant Protection*, 3(1): 22-30. <https://doi.org/10.24198/cropsaver.v3i1.28324>
- FAO and CABI (2019):** Community-Based Fall Armyworm Monitoring, Early Warning and Management: Training of Trainers Manual.
- Gahukar, R.T. (2014):** Factors affecting content and bio efficacy of neem (*Azadirachta indica* A, Juss.) phytochemicals used in agricultural pest control: A review. *J. of Crop Prot.*, 62: 93-99. doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2014.04.014
- Ghotbi, K. Ko. (2014):** Preparation of neem seed oil nanoemulsion Proceedings of the 5th International Conference of Nanotechnology 150.
- Gupta, V.K.; and Sharma, S.K. (2006):** Plants as Natural Antioxidants. *J. Nat. Prod. Rad.*, 5: 326-334.
- Habig, W. H.; Pabst, M. J. and Jakoby, W. B. (1974):** Glutathione S-Transferases the first enzymatic step in mercapturic acid formation. *J. of Bio. Chem.*, 249(22):7130-7139. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9258\(19\)42083-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9258(19)42083-8)
- Jerobin, J.; Sureshkumar, R.S.; Anjali, C.H.; Mukherjee, A. and Chandrasekaran, N. (2012):** Biodegradable polymer-based encapsulation of neem oil nanoemulsion for controlled release of Aza-A. *J. Carbohydrate Poly.*, 90(4): 1750-1756. doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2012.07.064
- Nawaz, M. and Mabubu, J. H. H. (2016):** Current status and advancement of biopesticides: microbial and botanical pesticides. *J. Entomol. Zool. Stud.*, 4: 241–246.
- Oberdörster, G.; Stone, V. and Donaldson, K. (2007):** Toxicology of nanoparticles: A historical perspective. *J. Nanotoxicol.*, 1(1):2–25. doi.org/10.1080/17435390701314761
- Pankaj, S.; Lokeshwar, T.; Mukesh, B. and Vishnu, B. (2011):** Review on neem (*Azadirachta indica*): Thousand problems one solution, *Int. J. Res. J. of Pharm.*, 2: 97–102.
- Paragas, D.S.; Cruz, K. and Fiegalan, E.R. (2018):** Assessment of green solvents and extraction methods for

- biopesticide preparation from neem *Azadirachta indica* leaves against oriental fruit fly *Bactrocera dorsalis* (Hendel). *J. Insects. Preprints*, 2018050179.
<https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints201805.0179.v1>
- Paul, R.; Prasad, M. and Sah, N.K. (2011):** Anticancer biology of *Azadirachta indica* L. (Neem): a mini review, *Canc. Biol. Ther.*, 12: 467–476. doi.org/10.4161/cbt.12.6.16850
- Rajashekar, Y.; Vijay Kumar, H.; Ravindra, K.V. and Bakthavatsalam, N. (2013):** Isolation and characterization of biofumigant from leaves of *Lantana camara* for control of stored grain insect pests. *J. Indus. Crop. and Prod.*, 51: 224–228. doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2013.09.006
- Rajendran, R.; Radhai, R.; Balakumar, C.; Ahamed, H.A.M.; Vigneswaran, C. and Vaideki, K. (2012):** Synthesis and Characterization of Neem Chitosan Nanocomposites for Development of Antimicrobial Cotton Textiles. *J. of Eng. Fib. and Fab.*, 7(1). doi:10.1177/15589250120070 0116
- Ramadhany, P.; Retti, J.; Witono, B. and Rosaria, R. (2021):** Neem-based oil-in-water (O/W) emulsion as a biopesticide. *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.*, 1053 012047. doi 10.1088/1757-899X/1053/1/012047
- Reitman, A. and Frankel, S. (1957):** A colorimetric method for the determination of serum glutamic oxalacetic and glutamic pyruvic transaminases. *Amer. J. of Clin. Path.*, 28(1): 56-63. doi:10.1093/ajcp/28.1.56
- Ren, T.; Li, R.; Zhao, L.; Fawcett, J.P.; Sun, D. and Gu, J. (2022):** Biological fate and interaction with cytochromes P450 of the nanocarrier material, D- α -tocopheryl polyethylene glycol 1000 succinate. *J. Acta Pharm Sin B.*, 12:3156–3166. doi:10.1016/j.apsb.2022.01.014
- Rinaldi, F.; Hanieh, P.N.; Longhi, C., et al. (2017):** Neem oil nanoemulsions: Characterisation and antioxidant activity. *J. Enzyme. Inhib. Med. Chem.*, 32 (1):1265–1273. doi:10.1080/14756366.2017.1378190
- Rinaldi, F.; Hanieh, P.N.; Maurizi, L.; Longhi, C.; Uccelletti, D.; Schifano, E.; Del Favero, E.; Cantù, L.; Ricci, C.; Ammendolia, M.G.; Paolino, D.; Froiio, F.; Marianecchi, C. and Carafa, M. (2022):** Neem oil or almond oil nanoemulsions for vitamin E delivery: from structural evaluation to in vivo assessment of antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity. *Int. J. Nanomedicine*, 17:6447-6465. <https://doaj.org/article/7d6a084a167e4bd9948ee7f190a08012>
- Sarkar, S.; Singh, R.P. and Bhattacharya, G. (2021):** Exploring the role of *Azadirachta indica* (Neem) and its active compounds in the regulation of biological pathways: an update on molecular approach. *J. Biotech.*, 11(4):1–12. doi:10.1007/s13205-021-02745-4
- Schmutterer, H. (1990):** Properties and potential of natural pesticides from the neem tree, *Azadirachta indica*. *J. Annu. Rev. Entomol.*, 35: 271–297. doi.org/10.1146/annurev.en.35.010190001415
- Sukontason, K.; Sukontason, K.L.; Ngern-Klun, R.; Sripakdee, D. and Piangjai, S. (2004):** Differentiation of the third instar of forensically important fly species in Thailand. *J. Ann. Entomol. Soc. Am.*, 97(6):1069–1075. [https://doi.org/10.1603/0013-8746\(2004\)097\[1069:DO TTIO\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1603/0013-8746(2004)097[1069:DO TTIO]2.0.CO;2)

Tadros, T. (2012): Emulsion formation and stability book, Wiley-VCH. doi: 10.1002/9783527 647941.ch8

Tobias, G J.; McLaughlin, R F. and Hopper, J. (1962): Endogenous creatinine clearance a valuable clinical test of glomerular filtration and a prognostic guide in chronic renal disease. The New England J. of Med., 266: 317-323. doi: 10.1056/NEJM196202152660701

Tulashie, S.K.; Adjei, F.; Abraham, J. and Addo, E. (2021): Potential of neem extracts as natural insecticide against fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), Case Studies in Chemical and Environmental Engineering, 4:100130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscee.2021.100130>